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Integration of TPC monitoring and control "LV" and "HV" subsystems to the Multi-Purpose Detector control system

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Abstract

The MPD detector is one of two detectors of the Nuclotron-based Ion Collider Facility (NICA) collider. The MPD is tracked by the time-based projection chamber (TPC). The OPC UA server protocol and CAEN devices serve as the foundation for the TPC LV and HV systems. Both high voltage (HV) and low voltage (LV) control and monitoring were performed with the Master-Scada 4D. Lazarus software serves as the foundation for both the MPD detector control system (DCS) and the Distributed Information Management (DIM) protocol. The integration status between MPD DCS and the TPC LV and HV subsystems is shown.

Introduction

The Joint Institute for Nuclear Research (JINR) constructed the new accelerator complex known as NICA in order to investigate the properties of dense baryonic matter. Protons, polarized deuterons, and heavy gold ions are among the beam species that NICA will provide. Heavy ions kinetic energy can reach 4.5 GeV per nucleon, while protons can reach 12.6 GeV [2]. The Time Projection Chamber (TPC) is one of the main tracking detectors for charge particles in the MPD experiment. The momentum resolution ($dP/P < 3\%$) and energy resolution ($dE/E \leq 8\%$) are

achieved by the solenoid magnetic field and TPC design [1].

Methodology

One of the primary tracking detectors for charge particles in the MPD experiment is the Time Projection Chamber (TPC). The solenoid magnetic field and TPC design achieve the energy resolution ($dE/E \leq 8\%$) and momentum resolution ($dP/P < 3\%$) [1]. The common perspective of TPC and LV+HV subsystems is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Common view of TPC with two flanges of ROC on its endcaps with HV electrode - in the center (red).

There are twelve ROC chambers on each TPC endcap. The anode of each ROC chamber was divided into four parts. Each component has its own HV channel for power. As a result, the TPC HV system has 96 HV channels. For block ions flow from each ROC chamber to the TPC drift

volume used a triggered gating grid. The TPC GATE system has 48 HV channels.

The SY4527 system is CAEN's most recent It is the fully operational experimental version of a new line of power supply systems and a proposal in the field of low voltage power supply. This system outlines an entirely new approach to power generation and distribution by allowing the housing of multiple boards with different functions within a single mainframe. These boards include high/low voltage boards, branch controllers, which are used to control other distant generators and distributors, and generic I/O boards (temperature, pressure monitors, etc.). Figure 2 displays the test setup. The mainframe SY4527, The LV modules, crate Easy3000, power converter A3486, and controller A1676 form its base.

[3].

Figure 2: CAEN set up test configuration for low voltage modules and power converter A3486.

The system can be configured by connecting it directly to the local area network (LAN) via the Ethernet port on the PC. Following the instructions on the Dynamic Host Configuration Port, connect to the HIVOCS and set up the network after the PC has been given an IP address.

Results

The software tools OPC UA and Master SCADA 4D, along with the hardware-software interfaces, can be used to monitor and control the power

converter A3486, as well as the high and low voltage modules.

Master SCADA 4D is a product of a new generation of SCADA systems developed by the company “MPS soft”. A technological monitoring, control methods, and control windows for GUI Interface [4].

For LV and HV systems, the values characterizing their states and error messages come from the CAEN System and are automatically processed in Master-Scada 4D to then be read by the function block as shown in figures 3:5. Possible errors are (Over Current), UNV (Under Voltage), OVV (Over Voltage), OVT (Over Temperature), and no connection error [4].

Figure 3: Main window of GUI for TPC HV and LV subsystems (using Master SCADA 4D).

Figure 4: Example of GUI Interface for High Voltage.

The Master-Scada 4D control program includes: Current and voltage management for each channel, Control of current and voltage across a

group of channels within (one read out chamber configuration), side voltage control detectors

- Similarly done and power on and off
- The status of each read out chamber is tracked
- Implemented administration with assigning rights,
- The IP address of the computer from which the connection was made is tracked.

Figure 5: Example of ROC chamber window. current and voltage are controlled via 5 channels (4 positive and one negative) for HV system.

Figure 6: Low Voltage Graphic User Interface using Master SCADA 4D.

Integration of DIM server to Master-Scada 4D system for control and monitoring of all TPC subsystems

Towards ensure communication, a function block for Master-SCADA 4D was developed and implemented (DIM server). For communication between the visualization and control systems Master-Scada 4D and MPD DCS, the DIM

protocol (Distributed Information Management System) interface was chosen.

DIM is a portable and compact package for publishing information, transferring data, and communicating amongst processes. Clients typically only make one service request (at startup), and the server automatically updates them either on a regular basis or whenever conditions change.

Servers publish their services by registering them under the Publish server, while clients "subscribe" to them by contacting the server directly, as depicted in figure 7.

- Server presents a “hardware view” of subsystem in terms “rack-crate-module-channel”
- Server works with hardware at the subdetector TPC.
- Server should be controlled only by the subdetector experts
- Server could support many clients

Figure 7: the interactions between the Publish Server, Clients, and Servers using DIM.

In order to control the statuses of the many TPC subsystems, the DIM server first initializes and creates services and instructions. Special DIM commands are used to carry out tasks like loading operating and parking parameters or turning on and off all power supplies. Figure 8 illustrates how DIM services, which are updated in real time, communicate each subsystem's condition information.

Figure 8: MPD Detector Control System Structure.

Numerous methods for starting the server, processing commands, updating service messages, controlling the state of the subsystems, accounting for time parameters, and using timers are all included in the C++ software block. The TPC Master-Scada 4D concept with DIM and MPD DCS windows is demonstrated in Figure 8 with subsystem examples, including HV, LV, Cooling, and Laser Systems. The "State" and "Message" fields in the Master-Scada 4D window are identified as manually defined.

In this instance, the entered values are shown in MPD DCS, where the message is shown next to the item and the state is represented by color, in addition to being published on the server. Additionally, Figure 9 demonstrates that HV is presently in a transient state, meaning that the power supplies are experiencing a voltage dip or rise.

Figure 9: Example of the current state of the nodes in the MPD DCS tree. MPD installation can have the following value:

- 1 - Node's state is not examined in any manner, nor is it color-coded.
- 0 - "Off" condition. At the hardware level, one of the nodes in the subtree is not responding.

- 1 - "Std By" condition. The subtree contains one node that is in the "Stand-by" state.
- 2 - "Not Rdy" condition. The subtree has a node that is in a transitory state.
- 3 - "Ready" condition. All subsystems are operating in the proper manner once the startup instruction was completed. It is possible to execute the data set.
- 4 - "Wrong" is the pre-alarm condition. The alarm state is almost reached by one of the system's nodes.
- 5 - "Error" alarm condition. The data set needs to be halted since one of the system's nodes has gone into an alarm state.

Conclusion

Master Scada 4D is baseline software for control and monitoring of TPC. GUI interface based on Master SCADA 4D and the CAEN OPC server for TPC HV and LV subsystems. For interaction between the visualization and control system of Master-SCADA 4D and MPD DCS, the protocol DIM was chosen. DIM server was implemented to Master SCADA 4D. Lazarus software was chosen for MPD DCS. Example of MPD DCS GUI for TPC presented.

References

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